

A Step Ahead: Proposal for an Online Data-base of the Organizations Working with CWSN

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It started with a suggestion to put together a list of organizations working for children with special needs (hereafter, CWSN). A quick review of the existing platforms such as NGO Darpan, Udaan, Saathire etc, revealed that a well-organized data-base already existed, usually providing, websites of the organizations working for CWSN, contact information, summary of their contribution to the field, accreditations/affiliations, year of establishment etc. These were mostly organised and searchable location-wise/alphabetically/by name of the organization.

As I began having a closer look at websites of these organizations, what caught my attention was the wide range of interventions set-up and offered by these organizations; creating formal and non-formal learning spaces that can cater to the special needs, to equip these spaces by providing required professional support through teacher education, infrastructural facilities, specially designed curriculum, teaching-learning materials etc. Many of them also offered early intervention, assessment of the child, diagnosis of the special need(s), counselling, therapy and professional support to the parents and families.

Some of the organizations created independent learning spaces, while some offered interventions at multiple levels to help existing formal learning spaces i.e, schools to become inclusive spaces, well-equipped to cater to various special needs. In the latter category as well, the interventions varied from preparing children to enter the mainstream education system and supporting those who have already entered the schooling, to help schools to create resource rooms, prepare the teachers and adapt the inclusive approach to education, creating inclusive curricular material etc (Action for Autism, Inclusive Centre for Education, Kilikili, Orkids, Sol's Arc, Sethu, Sarthak Education Trust, Urmi foundation to name a few). The two that I particularly found quite interesting were; the one that aimed at helping CWSN develop

social skills and the other was the one that aimed at creating inclusive play spaces.

Based on the varieties at various levels that I learnt about while reviewing these organizations, I would like to suggest some modifications in the existing platforms, to make them more user-friendly. In addition to the facility that allows to search for organizations geography-wise, or alphabetically, if some more searchable categories can be introduced, such as; the types of intervention, disabilities taken care of by the interventions, separate categories for organizations working towards creating inclusive learning spaces etc.

Apart from an exhaustive list of organizations under-preparation, what else this effort left for me was a question cum thought; how if the organizations specialised in different types of interventions come together to develop a replicable model of an inclusive learning space? Will that ensure an exhaustive implementation of the inclusive approach in the formal schooling system? If such models replicated across the states, will that sort of help the current issue of making the learning process accessible, meaningful and engaging for all?

1. Aakanksha Lions Institute for learning and empowerment, Raipur, Chhattisgarh.

Year of establishment: 1994

The institute works with the children and teachers in school and offers out-of-school interventions. It specializes in providing education and therapy to persons with cerebral palsy, autism, deaf-blindness and multiple disabilities.

Address: Avanti Vihar, Raipur (C.G) 492006

Email address: aakankshalsmh@yahoo.com

Contact numbers: 0771-2443761; 0771-4035441; 0771-4013771

2. Aarambh Autism Center, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India

Year of establishment: 2011

The school works with children, provides support to parents and offers courses and workshops. It specializes in providing education, therapy and support to children with autism.

Address: No. 24, Mhada Colony, Shah Noor Dargah Road, Shahnoorwadi, Aurangabad-431 006, Maharashtra

Email address: ambikanidhu@gmail.com

Contact number: +91 8275284178

3. Aasraa Trust, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Year of establishment: 2009

This is a special needs centre.

Address: 119/1 Vasant Vihar, Dehradun 248006, Uttarakhand India

Email address: aasraa@aasraatrust.org ; <https://aasraatrust.org/contact/>

Website: <https://aasraatrust.org/special-needs-center/>

Contact number: 91-9045056991

4. Academy for Severe Handicaps and Autism (ASHAA), Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 1995

This is an assessment, training and guidance center for children above the age of two. The center specializes in assessment, counseling and therapy for children with learning difficulties, hyperactivity and mild autism.

Address: #287, 5th Main, 11th Cross, Mahalaxmi Layout, Bangalore - 560086; L-76/A Kirloskar Colony, 3rd Cross, 5th Main, 4th Block, Basaveshwarnagar, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India, 560079

Email address: atg.asha@gmail.com

Website: <https://www.ashaforautism.com>

Contact number: +91 - 080-23225279; +91 - 23230357

5. Action for Autism – Delhi

Year of establishment: 1991

This organization provides support to parents of children with autism.

Address: The National Centre for Autism, Pocket 7 & 8, Jasola Vihar, New Delhi 110 025, India

Email address: actionforautism@gmail.com

Contact number: + 91 11 4054 0991; + 91 11 4054 0992

6. ADAPT (formerly known as The Spastics Society of India), Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1972

This is an NGO working with students (mainly young adults) and parents; provides courses, assessment & counseling services for individuals with cerebral palsy, autism, mental retardation, multiple disabilities and learning disabilities.

Address: ADAPT- Centre for special education, Upper Colaba road, opposite Afgan church, Mumbai, Maharashtra-400005

Website: <http://adaptssi.org>

Contact number: 2222150555; 2222185338

7. Adarsh Charitable Trust, Cochin, Kerala

Year of establishment: 1998

The trust runs a school for children below the age of 6 years who may be suffering from autism, cerebral palsy, down's syndrome and learning disorders.

Address: Adarsh Charitable Trust, X/584 B, Puthiya Road, Opposite Agasthya Ashram, Kureekkad-682 305, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

Email address: adarshrehab@yahoo.com

Website: www.adarshrehab.org

Contact number: +91 484 2794099

8. All Manipur Mentally Handicapped Persons Welfare Organization, Imphal, Manipur

Year of establishment: 2016

Runs a school for children with intellectual disability.

Email address: amhokeishamthong@gmail.com

Contact number: 9612161803

9. Ambuja Manovikas Kendra by Ambuja Cement Foundation, Punjab (Location of the intervention) Mumbai, Maharashtra (Headquarters)

Year of establishment: 1993

It is a school run in Punjab for children with special needs.

Address: Elegant Business Park, MIDC Cross Road 'B', Off Andheri-Kurla Road, Andheri (E), Mumbai 400059

Contact number: 022 - 40667520; +91 98333 48602

10. Amrit Foundation, Delhi

Year of establishment: 2012

The foundation supports education for children with Autism Spectrum Disorder, Cerebral Palsy, Down's syndrome and intellectual disability.

Address: Amrit Foundation Of India, Farm no. 31, Saraswati Farms 100 Ft. Road, Ghitori, New Delhi – 110030

Email address: team@amritindia.in

Website: <https://amritfoundationofindia.in>

Contact number: +91-11 26520998; +91-11 40634810

11. Ananya Child Development Centre, Hyderabad, Telangana

Year of establishment: 2002 (estimated)

It is an intervention centre that supports children and parents. The centre specializes in therapy, assessment and counselling.

Address: Hightech Chambers, 55/A, Jubilee Enclave, Madhapur, Hyderabad - 500 081, Telangana; 101 Orion Plaza, Rd No. 3, Resham Bagh, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad - 500 034, Telangana; Lane 22, Plot No. 39, Prashanth Hills, Manikonda, Hyderabad-500008, Telangana

Email address: info@asap.org.in

Website: <https://www.asap.org.in>

Contact number: +91 98485 13192

12. Ankur Special School, Korba, Chhattisgarh

Year of establishment: 2013

It is a special school for children between the age of 4 and 10 years.

Address: Korba Mudapar, S.E.C.L., (C.G.), behind Ambedkar Bhavan, Korba, Chhattisgarh 495677

Contact number: 077592 15871

13. Arushi, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

Year of establishment: 1989- Early 1990's

Arushi, provides intervention and training for children and teachers.

Website: <https://www.arushi-india.org>

14. Arvi Trust, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Year of establishment: 1995

This organization provides home-based learning and open schooling facilities for children with hearing impairment and intellectual disabilities.

Address: Laxmi Nagar, Seelapadi, Dindigul - 624005, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email address: arvitrust@gmail.com

Website: <http://arvitrust.org>

Contact number: +91 98431 60475; +91 94421 60475

15. Ashadeep, Guwahati, Assam

Year of establishment: 1996-97 (estmtd.)

Ashadeep is a Day Rehabilitation Centre for children with intellectual disabilities.

Address: Piya Apartments, Kanaklata Path, Lachitnagar, Guwahati 781 007, Assam, India

Email address: societyashadeep@yahoo.com

Website: <http://www.ashadeepindia.org>

Contact number: 91- 94350 43308; (91)-(361)-2456837

16. Ashray Akriti, Hyderabad, Telangana

Year of establishment: 1996

Email address: info@ashrayakriti.in

17. Assam Autism Foundation (AAF), Guwahati, Assam

Year of establishment: 1998

The foundation works with children. It's a day care centre that works with children who have developmental disabilities with a special focus on autism.

Address: 10, "Anandam", Lokheshwar Baruah Path, near FCI gate, Hanuram Mandir, New Guwahati, Noonmatiand Guwahati 781020.

Email address: autiassam@gmail.com; shabinaloveschildren@gmail.com

Website: www.aaf.org.in

Contact number: +91- 9706014608; +91-9706042918; +91- 9864027292

18. ASTHA (Alternative Strategies for the Handicapped), New Delhi

Year of establishment: early 1990s

The organization provides support to school children and parents; offers courses & workshops; assessment & therapy services.

Email address: aarthindia@gmail.com

Website: <https://asthaindia.in>

Contact number: 011-26449026

19. Astitva, Dombivali, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1981

It is a school for children with mild/moderate/severe mental retardation, Down syndrome, epilepsy, cerebral palsy, birth asphyxia, hyperactive etc. and for children with hearing impairment.

Address: 'ASTITVA' 8 A, MIDC, Dombivli (E) 421 203, Thane, Maharashtra, India

Email address: astitvatrust81@gmail.com

Website: <https://www.astitvaschool.co.in/>

Contact number: +91-251-2471358

20. Bal Badhit Vikas Kendra, Hadauti District, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 1975

This is a school up to class X for children with visual and hearing impairment.

Website: <http://www.bbvk.org/>

21. Bhairabi Club, Kurum Pada, Odisha

Year of establishment: 1997

The bhairabi club provides educational facilities from pre-primary to vocational for the intellectually challenged; and preparatory to standard-viii for hearing & visually impaired children.

Address: Bhairabi Club, Kurumpada, PO-Hadapada Dist. Khordha, Orissa- 752 018

Email address: indo@bhairabiclub.org, bhairabi_27@yahoo.co.in, bhairabicluborissa@gmail.com

Website: <http://bhairabiclub.org/>

Contact number: 06755-245027

22. Bharat Jyoti, Cuttack, Odisha

Year of establishment: 2002

This is a higher secondary school for children with mental retardation, multiple disability, visually impairment and the hearing & speech impaired.

Website: <https://bharatjyotiodisha.org>

Address: Bharat Jyoti, Jhanjirimangala, (S.B.I. Building) Telengabazarand Cuttack Odisha, India Pin: 753009

Email address: info@bharatjyotiodisha.org

Contact number: 91 99371 91097 / +91 8763423735; 91 671-2349622

23. Bihar Netrahin Parishad, Patna, Bihar

Year of establishment: 1981

This is a girl's only school for children with visual impairment.

Address: Bihar Netraheen Parishad, Near panchsheel High School Kumhrar, Patna Pincode: 800026

Contact number: 9470851776; 0612-2352415

24. Brindavan Education Trust, Bangalore, Karnataka

The trust runs a school for children with specific learning difficulties.

Address: 456, 9th Main Rd, 2nd Block, Jayanagar, Bengaluru, Karnataka 560011

Email address: brindavansld@gmail.com

Contact number: 080 2664 0363

25. Care4autism, Secunderabad, Telangana

Year of establishment: 2009

Care4autism offers support to parents and educational programmes for children of all ages with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), speech-language difficulties and learning difficulties (LD) including underachievement, dyslexia, dyspraxia, sensory integration difficulties, speech language difficulties and auditory processing disorders (APD).

Website: <http://www.care4autism.in>

Address: CFA Society, O/o Care4Autism Center, 20/21 Triveni Colony

Bolarum, Secunderabad 500010, Telangana, INDIA

Email address: autisticsociety@gmail.com ; simplygive@ymail.com ; askneetu@gmail.com

Contact number: 9849884321; 040-27862310

26. CATCH (Center for Autism Therapy, Counseling and Help), Bhubaneswar, Odisha

Year of establishment: 2003

This is a voluntary parent support group for parent of children with autism.

Website: <https://catchindia.org.in/>

Address: K-8/263, Kalinga Nagar, Near Sum Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India

Email address: jenareeta@hotmail.com

Contact number: 91 9937004040

27. CBR NETWORK, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 1992

Website: <https://cbr-network.org/>

Address: Global Partnership for Disability and Development 134,1st Block, 6th Main, BSK III Stage Bangalore-560085, India

Email address: bucbr@hotmail.com;
ideasianetwork2013@gmail.com;
bucbr@outlook.com

Contact number: 91(India)-80(Bangalore)-26724273, 26724221

28. Communication Deall, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 2000

The organization provides an early intervention programme, along with assessment, counseling and therapy for 2-6 years old children.

Website: <https://www.communicationdeall.com>

Address: 224, 6th 'A' Main, II Block, HRBR Layout, Bangalore 560043.

Email address: communicationdeall@gmail.com

Contact number: 080-25800826 / 27; 94803-34809

29. Darpan School, Ludhiana, Punjab

Year of establishment: 2015

It's a special education, assessment and training center.

Website: <https://darpanautism.org/>

Address: 2819, Pakhowal Rd, Gurdev Nagar, Ludhiana, Punjab 141001

Email address: darpanautism@hotmail.com

Contact number: +91 9779913463; +91 9417160463

30. Deepalaya, Delhi

Year of establishment: 1998-99

Learning centre for children with intellectual disability, cerebral palsy, down syndrome, autism, hearing and speech impaired, muscular dystrophy and other physical impairments.

Website: <https://www.deepalaya.org/>

Address: 46, organizational Area, D Block, Janakpuri, New Delhi 110058

Email address: kalpanadas@deepalaya.org

Contact number: 011-64719557

31. Devnar foundation for the Blind, Hyderabad, Telangana

Year of establishment: 1991

It is a school up to class XII for the children with visual impairment.

Website: <http://www.devnarfoundationfortheblind.org/>

Address: Devnar School for The Blind Mayuri Marg, Begumpet Hyderabad – 500026

Email address: saibaba_goud@hotmail.com

Contact number: (+91) 040 66175696

32. Dilkhush Special School, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1971

This is a school for special children 5-16 years of age.

Website: <http://dilkhush.org.in/>

Address: Dilkhush Special School, Juhu Tara Road, Mumbai 400 049

Email address: dilkhushjuhu@yahoo.com

Contact number: +91-22-2615 1304

33. Dwar Jingkyrmen School for children in need of Special Education, Shillong, Meghalaya

Year of establishment: 1986

The school works with children in need of special education and parents of such children.

Website: <http://megscpwd.gov.in/dwarjingkyrmen/about-us.html>

Email address: dwar_jingkyrmen@rediffmail.com

Contact number: +91364 2221226

34. EnAble India, Bangalore, Karnataka

Website: <https://www.enableindia.org/>

Address: 473/B, Adugodi Main Road, 8th Block, Koramangala, Bengaluru, Karnataka 560095

35. Humanity Welfare Organization Helpline, Anantnag, Jammu and Kashmir

Year of establishment: 2003

This organization works with children in and out of school. It provides for assessment, counseling and therapy for the children with hearing, visual, intellectual and orthopedic disabilities.

Website: <http://www.humanitywelfarehelpline.org>

Address: National Highway Road, Bijbehara Anantnag (J & K), Pin- 192124

Email address: jsocialactivist@gmail.com, sajad1920@yahoo.co.in

Contact number: 09469064964, 09419746398

36. Inclusive Centre of Education, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2004

This is a learning and therapy centre that works with children, adolescents and adults with special needs. It provides for assessment, counseling and therapy and curriculum materials.

Website: <http://inclusivecentre.org/>

Address: Kush Regency, Gala No 1, Post - Office Lane, Behind Apna Bazaar, J.P Road, Andheri (West) Mumbai-400053

Email address: inclusivecentre@rocketmail.com

Contact number: +91 - 9322192137; +91 - 9892071300

37. Indi ability Foundation, Jodhpur, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 2011

The foundation provides for school-based engagement for children with physical disabilities.

Website: <https://www.indiability.org>

Address: 81 Virendra Nagar, C Sector, Mandore Road, Jodhpur 342 304, Rajasthan India ; DD-30, 2nd floor (back entrance), Nehru Enclave, Kalkaji, New Delhi 110019 India

Contact number: +91 11 4163 9050; +91 11 2621 9050; +91 (0)9829 595 500; +91 (0)9413 331 700

38. Indian Institute of Cerebral Palsy, Kolkata, West Bengal

Year of establishment: 1974

This is a specialist resource centre that works with cerebral palsy affected children and their parents, provides with services for assessment, counseling and therapy.

Website: <http://www.iicpindia.org/>

39. Integrated High School, Narasaraopet, Guntur District Andhra Pradesh

Year of establishment: 1985

This is a school for children with hearing impairment and intellectual disabilities.

Website: <http://integratedhighschool.in/>

Address: APV Indira Rao / Director, Vallapacheruvu Road, near Dharga Narasaraopet, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh 522601, India

Email address: info@integratedhighschool.in

Contact number: 08647-220237 ; 98-48168578

40. Janey Centre, Cochin, Kerala

Year of establishment: 2015

This is a Rehabilitation center with assessment, therapy and training services. It offers NIOS affiliated formal learning, as well as pre-vocational and vocational training courses.

Website: <https://www.janeycentre.com/>

Address: Janey Nagar, Eloor-Kochi-682306 Kerala-India

Contact number: 0484-2778906/9539181020

41. Kamla Mehta Dadar School for Blind, Dadar, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1900

This school is from Kindergarten to class X for the visually challenged girls.

Address: No. 160, Dadasaheb Phalke Road, Dadar East, near Tata Mill, Mumbai, Maharashtra 400014

Contact number: 022 2418 3144

42. KARAM MANOVIKAS SANSTHAN, Alwar, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 2000

This is an educational organization.

Address: B- Block Budhvihar Alwar (Raj)
301001

Email address: kmvsansthan@gmail.com

Contact number: 09414240645 ; 0144-2732940

43. Khushboo Welfare Society, Gurgaon, Haryana

Year of establishment: 1995

It provides facilities of a school, therapy, training and learning centre for children, young adults and adults with cerebral palsy, down syndrome, autism, mental retardation and slow learners.

Website: <http://www.kwsindia.org>

Address: Khushboo Welfare Society | Plot no-2, Sector-10A, Near Lions Public School, Gurugram, Haryana – 122001, India

E m a i l a d d r e s s :
Khushboowelfaresociety@kwsindia.org

Contact number: 91-124-4140885/86/87

44. Kilikili, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Year of establishment: 2006

It is an organization working towards creating inclusive play spaces.

Website: <https://www.kilikili.org>

Address: 2 C, Baywatch Apts, 20, New Beach Road, Thiruvalluvar Nagar, Thiruvanmiyur, Chennai 600041

Email address: info@kilikili.org

Contact number: 98807 42028

45. Latika Roy Foundation, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Year of establishment: 1994

The foundation runs a special school and provides for daycare, early intervention and home-based programmes for children up to the age of 15 years.

Website: <https://latikaroy.org/>

Address: 113/1, Vasant Vihar, Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India

Email address: sumita@latikaroy.org

Contact number: 91-135-2761014 ; 843 9000 110

46. Madras Dyslexia Association, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Year of establishment: 1992

The association provides courses & workshops for 3 to 12-year-old children with Dyslexia.

Website: <https://www.mdachennai.com>

Address: Landmark - JJ Diamonds, 94, 1st Floor, Park View Complex, Park View Road (Jeeva Park, Gopathi Narayanaswami Chetty Rd, T Nagar, Parthasarathi Puram, T. Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu 600017

E m a i l a d d r e s s :
madras.dyslexia.association17@gmail.com

Contact number: 044-28157908 / 044-28156697
FOR INQUIRIES ABOUT ASSESSMENTS
CALL:
+91 9445567908

47. Manovikas Kendra, Kolkata, West Bengal

Year of establishment: 2000

It is a charitable society running schools, care centers and institutes for higher education for children ages 4-5 years (approx.) and above. it facilitates assessment, counseling and therapy for children with intellectual challenge, autism spectrum disorder and hearing impairment etc.

Website: <http://manovikaskendra.org>

Address: 482, Madudah, Plot: I-24, Sector : J, E.M.Bypass, Kolkata 700 107, WB, India.

Email address: mvkendra1974@gmail.com

Contact number: +91 033-4001 2731 ; 033-4001 2732-35; 033 46031861

48. Marga Darshi Foundation, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 1988

This NGO works towards providing early intervention, therapy, counseling and financial support to the students with Physical disabilities.

Website: <http://www.margarshionline.org/>

Address: # 75/6, Hulkul Complex, Lalbagh Road, Bangalore – 560 027

Email address: marga_darshi@yahoo.co.in

Contact number: 080-2223 5810 ; +91 9243043413

49. Mentaid, Kolkata, West Bengal

Year of establishment: 1985

It is a school for children aged 3 and above.

Website: <https://mentaid.org/>

Address: 98N, Block E, New Alipore, Kolkata 700 053

Email address: mentaid@vsnl.net, mentaid.org@gmail.com

Contact number: (033) 2396 9510, 2399 5688

50. Mind Tree Foundation, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 2007

This foundation in collaboration with SPASTN, runs community-based Rehab centers to provide children with disabilities early detection, early intervention, physiotherapy and school readiness interventions.

Address: Mindtree Foundation. Global Village, RVCE Post, Mysore Road, Bengaluru – 560059, Karnataka, India

Email address: Foundation@mindtree.com

Contact number: 918067064888

51. Nambikkai Nilayam (Facility for children with intellectual disability), Vellore, Tamil Nadu

The facility works for children with intellectual disability and other neurodevelopmental conditions like autism, cerebral palsy and specific learning disabilities.

Website: <https://www.cmch-vellore.edu>

Address: Child and Adolescent Psychiatry Unit Office, Department of Psychiatry, Christian Medical College, Bagayam, Vellore - 632 002, Tamil Nadu.

52. Navjivni, Patiala, Punjab

Year of establishment: 1981

It's a school from Nursery to class VIII.

Website: <https://navjivini.com/>

Address: Navjivini School Of Special Education, Sular, Patiala-147001, Punjab

- Email address: navjivinischool@yahoo.com

- Contact number: 0175-2213517; (+91) 99883-16100

53. Netraheen Va Viklang Shikshan Prashikshan Evam Dharmarth Samithi, Korea Dst, Chhattisgarh

This is a school for the visually challenged children.

- Address: Aamakherava, Manendergarh, Dist.Korea, Chhattisgarh

54. Orkids Foundation, Delhi

Year of establishment: 2000

This organization aims to support schools practice inclusivity by setting-up resource centers in the schools, conducting assessments etc. Also offers early intervention, NIOS support classes for children above 14 years of age and teacher training for children with special needs.

- Website: <http://www.orkids.in/>

- Address: E-123, Kalkaji, New Delhi 110019

- Contact number: 011- -40584122

55. PARIVAAR - National Confederation of Parents Organizations, Pune, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1995

This is a federation of parents associations and civil societies for persons with intellectual and developmental disabilities.

- Website: <http://www.parivaarnfpa.org/>

- Address: A-1 Green Acres CHS, Salunke Vihar Road, PUNE-411048

- Email address: parivaarncpo@gmail.com

- Contact number: +91 2048603437

56. Pavani Special School, Visakhapatnam

Year of establishment: 1987

This is a school for children with mental disabilities and hearing impairment.

Website: <http://pavanispecialschool.org/>

Address: IMHANS, D.No. 49-34-25, Akkayyapalem Main Road, Visakhapatnam – 530016

Contact number: +91 891 2797821; +91 9885035467

57. Prafull Oorja, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 2011

This is a yoga therapy centre for children with special needs.

Address: Room 5, Sai Business Centre, 328, Stage Rd, Indiranagar, Bengaluru, Karnataka 560038

Email address: prafulloorja@gmail.com

Contact number: 078294 27742

58. Prasanna Autism Centre, Pune, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2012

It is a Development centre with assessment, consultancy and training services for autistic children aged 3-17 years.

Website: <http://www.prasannaautismcentre.com>

Address: 895, Shivaji Nagar, Deccan Gymkhana, Pune – 411004

Email address: hello@prasannaautismcentre.com

Contact number: +91 93260 13744 / 020-25652246

59. Prayas, Jaipur, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 1996

The organization works with children at school and outside school; provides counseling and therapy.

Website: <http://www.prayasjaipur.com/schools.html>

Address: Jhalana Special School (Head Office) J-5A, Jhalana organizational Area, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Raja Park Integrated School
343, Lane No. 2, Raja Park, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Amargarh Integrated School
Vedpuri, Parwat Colony, Amargarh, Transport Nagar, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

Sanganer Integrated School
26/17, Subhash Colony, Shikarpura Road, Sanganer, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Contact number: +91-141-2711018; +91-141-2624032; +91-141-2641103; +91-141-2733838

60. Rajasthan Mahila Kalyan Mandal Sanstha (RMKMS), Ajmer, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 1987

RMKMS works with children aged 0-15 years.

Website: <http://www.rmkm.org.in>

Address: "Vishwamitra Ashram" Village Chachiyawas, Sikar Road, District Ajmer Pin 305023 Rajasthan (India)

Email address: rmkm_ajm@yahoo.com, rmkm.a@rediffmail.com, info@rmkm.org.in

Contact number: +91-9829140992 ; +91-145-2794481

61. Rajkumari Amrit Kaur Center for Child Study, Delhi

Year of establishment: 1955

This is a pre-primary child study centre. It provides support for parents of children with special needs.

Website: <http://www.ladyirwin.edu.in/studycentre.aspx>

Address: LADY IRWIN COLLEGE, Sikandra Road, New Delhi - 110001

Email address: director@lic.du.ac.in

Contact number: 91-11-23711222

62. REACH, Kolkata, West Bengal

Year of establishment: 2006

This is a capacity building and resource organization for 3-14 year old children.

Website: <http://reach-india.org/>

Address: 18/2/A/3, Uday Sankar Sarani, Bikramgarh, Golf Green, Kolkata, West Bengal 700095

63. S P J Sadhna School, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1968

It is a school for 4 to 22 year old individuals with special needs.

Website: <http://spjsadhanaschool.org/>

Address: Sophia College Campus, Bhulabhai Desai Road, Mumbai 400 026

Email address: spjsadhana@gmail.com

Contact number: 022 2351 7913; 022 2351 0853

64. Sama Foundation, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 2005

The foundation works for children with disabilities.

Website: www.sama-foundation.org

Address: No.47/48 59th Cross 17th A Main, Rajajinagar 5th Block, Bangalore

Bengaluru (Bangalore) Urban, Karnataka, 560010

Email address: samafoundation@sama-foundation.org

Contact number: 91 - 80-23146058; 91 - 8861932132

65. SAMADHAN, Delhi

Year of establishment: 1981

The organization works with children who have intellectual disabilities and their parents.

Website: <https://samadhanindia.org/>

Address: F-Block Main Park (Near Durbalnath Mandir), Sector-V, Dakshinpuri, New Delhi - 110 062

Email address: samadhan.dwarka@gmail.com

Contact number: +91-11-2905 4367, +91-11-2605 6812

66. Samaj Unnayan Kendra (SUK), Sunderban region, West Bengal

Year of establishment: 1975

Website: <https://www.samajunnayankendra.org/>

Address: Vill+ P. O - Baribhangabad, Companirtheek, Pin- 743349, Dist.- 24 Pgs. West Bengal

Email address: suken10@gmail.com

67. Samerth, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

Year of establishment: 1992

The organization works for children with intellectual disability, Down syndrome, Autism, Cerebral Palsy, hearing and visual impairment and those with decampment delay. It provides assessment, counseling and therapy related services for such children.

Website: <https://www.samerth.org>

Address: Q-402, Shrinand Nagar Part-2, Shrinand Nagar, Vejalpur, Ahmedabad, Gujarat 380051

Email address: info@samerth.org

Contact number: 079 2682 9004

68. Sampoorna Music therapy, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 2013

It is a music therapy centre for individuals who have autism.

Website: <https://sampoornamusictherapy.wordpress.com/home/>

Address: No 35, 10th main, 6th cross, Nandanam Colony, Horamavu, Bangalore, 560043

Email address: sampoornamusic@gmail.com

Contact number: 9916111533 ; 080-40943390

69. Sangath, Goa

Year of establishment: 1996

The organization works with children at and outside schools and parents; provides for therapy & assessment.

Website: <https://www.sangath.in/>

Address: H No 451 (168), Bhatkar Waddo, Socorro, Porvorim, Bardez, Goa 403501

Email address: contactus@sangath.in

Contact number: 0091 7887872345

70. Sarthak Education Trust, New Delhi

Year of establishment: 2004

Website: <https://sarthakindia.org/>

Address: Sarthak Educational Trust Building No.1, Mohammadpur, Near Bhikaji Cama Place New Delhi – 110066 011-42004238

Email address: sarthakedu@gmail.com

suman.aggarwal@sarthakindia.org

pm.gurgaon@sarthakindia.org

pm.jaipur@sarthakindia.org

Contact number: 011-42004238 ; 011 - 47029325 ; 0141- 2703322 ; 0161-4504499

71. Sense International India, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

Year of establishment: 1997

The organization works with school children who are speech and hearing impaired.

Website: <https://www.senseintindia.org>

Address: Sense International India 2nd Floor, Administrative Block, Andhajan Mandal Campus, Opp. IIM, Vastrapur Ahmedabad- 380015

Email address: info@senseintindia.org

Contact number: 917926301282

72. Sethu, Goa

Year of establishment: 2005

The NGO provides therapy, assessment, training and has an intervention centre for children with developmental, behavioral, emotional and learning difficulties.

Website: <https://sethu.in>

Address: Sethu centre For child development and family guidance.

House No. 5/82, 5/84 & 5/48, Dhon Vaddo, Saligao, Bardez, North Goa 403511, India

Contact number: +91-77200 13749

73. Shishu Sarothi Services, Guwahati, Assam

Year of establishment: 1987

The organization provides day care and learning centre and teachers' training.

Website: <http://shishusarothi.org/>

Address: Off Ramkrishna Mission Road, Birubari, Guwahati - 781016, Assam, India

Email address: shishusarothi@gmail.com

Contact number: +91 9706080089 ; +91 9207049810

74. Shri Narsingh Maharaj Punarwas & Sikshan Sansathan (SNMPSS), Jaipur, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 2012

It is an educational organization for children (4-17 years) with developmental disabilities and autism.

Website: <http://www.snmjaipur.com>

Address: 9/199, Malviya Nagar, Jaipur-302017, Rajasthan

Email address: info@snmjaipur.com, skmeena@rediffmail.com

Contact number: +91-9414058796 ; +91-9829100637

75. Sir Shapurji Billimoria Foundation, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 1998

Address: Nanik Niwas Bldg. 2nd Flr. Flat No. 24, Warden Road, opposite Tata Garden, Mumbai, 400026

Email address: ritestep@gmail.com

Contact number: 022 2369 6596

76. SKSN: Sucheta Kriplani Shiksha Niketan, Near Jodhpur, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 1991

It is a school for children with physical disabilities.

Website: <http://sksn.org>

Address: SKSN: Sucheta Kriplani Shiksha Niketan

VPO Manaklao Via Mathania – Dist. Jodhpur ,Jodhpur 342 305, Rajasthan India ;

DD-30, 2nd floor / back entrance, Nehru Enclave (off Kalkaji Rd) Kalkaji, New Delhi 110 019

Contact number: + 91 94 6010 7502; + 91 94 6010 7505 ; +91 11 4163 9050 T/ +91 11 2621 9050

77. Society for Empowerment of the Disabled, Bishnupur district, Manipur

Year of establishment: 2008

It is a school and training centre for individuals with various disabilities.

Website: <https://www.sfedmanipur.org.in>

Address: Moirang Phiwangbam Leikai, Bishnupur District,Manipur, 795133

Email address: helpline@sfedmanipur.org.in queries@sfedmanipur.org.in

Contact number: 098627 17660

78. Society for the Welfare of Disabled

Year of establishment: 1989

This is a special school for children with physical and developmental disabilities such as mental retardation, cerebral palsy, specific learning disabilities, autism, attention deficit and hyperactive disorder (ADHD) and multiple disabilities.

Website: <http://megscpwd.gov.in/swd/about-us.html>

79. Sol's ARC, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2003

Sol's ARC has a model school and therapy centre setup for children with special needs. It provides counseling, assessment & therapy for these children.

Website: <https://solsarc.ngo/#>

Address: 1-A, Alisha Apartments, 4 Spence Lane
Next to Seva Niketan, Byculla,
Mumbai- 400008

Email address: contact@solsarc.ngo

Contact number: +91 22 26350834 ; +91
9867219041 ; '+91 9322699195

80. Sona Manovikas Kendra, Bhilwara, Rajasthan

Year of establishment: 1996

It is a school, therapy and training centre.

Website: <http://www.sonamanovikaskendra.com/>

Address: Behind Sophia Noble School, Kuwada
Road, Bhilwara, Rajasthan, 311001.

Email address: svnbhilwara@gmail.com ;
info@sonamanovikaskendra.com

Contact number: 94141122526; 01482-290444

81. SOPAN (Society of Parents of Children with Autistic Disorders), Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2002

SOPAN is an NGO that provides services that include diagnosis, counseling, early intervention, school education, therapies and vocational training. It has a school under construction for children with autism and associated developmental disabilities.

Website: <http://sopan.org/>

Address: B.M.C. School Building, Natwar Nagar
Road No.5, Jogeshwari (E), Mumbai – 400 060.

Email address: sopantrust@rediffmail.com
snacmah@gmail.com sopanasd@gmail.com
info@sopan.org

Contact number: 022 6504 3998 ; 91-22-6504
3998, 91-22-2832 83550, 91-22-6504 39980,
91-22-2832 8351, 91-93232 02768

82. Spastics Society of Karnataka, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 1981

The society has a day centre and provides early intervention and vocational training for persons with neuro-muscular and developmental disabilities.

Website: <https://www.spasticssocietyofkarnataka.org/>

Address: Spastics Society of Karnataka 31, 5th
Cross, Off 5th Main Road, Indiranagar, 1st
Stage, Bangalore-560 038

Email address: <https://www.spasticssocietyofkarnataka.org/contact-us-online> ;
office@spasticssocietyofkarnataka.org

Contact number: +91 (80) 4148 1777

83. Special Education Society, Vadodara, Gujarat

Year of establishment: 2011

SES offers non-formal education programme for children above six years of age.

Website: <http://sairesidentialschool.org/>

Address: Sai Residential School
56, Buddev Colony Rd, Near M.I.G. Flats,
Sampark Parivar MIG Colony, Buddh Dev
Colony, Kareligh, Vadodara, Gujarat 390001

Email address: sairesidentialschool@yahoo.in

Contact number: +91 99041 33880; 99246
02199; 0265 248 2504

84. Srijan Foundation, Ranchi, Jharkhand

Year of establishment: 2001

Website: <http://www.srijan-jhk.org/home/>

<https://www.srijanjhk.org/>

Address: Srijan Foundation, 106, Bijoy Enclave,
Heerabag Chowk, Matwari, Hazaribag – 825301

Email address: info@srijanjhk.org

Contact number: 06546-270523 | 263787

85. Sukarya, Gurgaon, Haryana

Year of establishment: 1998

Website: <https://sukarya.org>

Address: Sukarya, Near Paras Hospital and
Shallom Hills International School, Block E,
Sushant Lok, Phase I, Gurugram – 122002,
Haryana, India

Email address: sukarya@sukarya.org
Shipra.shukla@sukarya.org

Contact number: +91-0124-4114251;
+91-0124-4114253; 91-9999918517;
+91-9910248487

86. Tactopus, Bangalore, Karnataka

Tactopus is creator of learning resources and platforms connecting parents to specialists for

the Visually challenged children and children with low vision.

Website: <https://tactopus.com/>

Address: Social Alpha, no 3, 14th main, HSR Layout 5th Sector, Above HDFC bank, Bangalore

Email address: hello@tactopus.com

Contact number: +91 80566 68943

87. Tamanna Foundation, Delhi

Year of establishment: 1984

It is a special education Centre for 4-17-year-old children with multiple disabilities and Autism. It provides facilities for counseling and therapy as well.

Website: <http://www.tamana.org>

Address: CPWD Complex, Near Chinmaya Vidyalaya, Vasant Vihar, New Delhi ; Tamana Special School, D-6 street Vasant Vihar, New Delhi 110057

Email address: info@tamana.org
ttc@tamana.ngo rashmiwahi@tamana.ngo

Contact number: 26143843 ; 26153474 ; 011 26151572

88. Tanay Foundation, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

Email address: info@tanayfoundation.org

Contact number: +91 97128 50173 ; 9712850082

89. Tapovan Manovikas Kendra, Sri-Ganganagar, Rajasthan

Website: <http://www.tapovanmanovikas.org/>

Address: 4ML, Suratgarh Road, Near Homeland City , Sri-Ganganagar- 335001

Email address: tapovancollege@gmail.com
tapovanmanovikas@rediffmail.com

90. The Aadhaar Centre, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

Year of establishment: 2004

The Aadhaar Centre is a child welfare organization. It includes Doctors, therapists & professional counselors.

Website: <http://aadhaarcentre.org>

Address: E-3 Senior MIG 12 Arera Colony Near Bhopal Fracture Hospital Bhopal-462016.

Email address: aadhaarcentre@gmail.com
info@aadhaarcentre.org

Contact number: +91 755 4275551, 4258622, +91 9109548885

91. The Association of People With Disability, Bangalore, Karnataka

Year of establishment: 1959

The organization works for children with disabilities below 16-years of age, from the economically marginalized and deprived communities.

Website: <https://www.apd-india.org>

Address: The Association of People with Disability 6th Cross, Hutchins Road, Off, Hennur Road, Lingarajapuram, St. Thomas Town Post Bangalore-560 084,

- Email address: contact@apd-india.org

- Contact number: (+91 80) 25475165

92. UDAI, New Delhi

Year of establishment: 2013

The organization works for children with special needs.

- Website: <https://www.udai.org.in/>

- Address: B 1/20, Janakpuri, Near Amarleela Hospital, New Delhi - 58

- Email address: udai.march@gmail.com

- Contact number: (+91 11) 4107-9384 ; 91 9899681972

93. Uma Trust, Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh

Year of establishment: 1988

This Trust provides support to children with intellectual and developmental disabilities, hearing and visual impairments.

- Website: <http://www.uetsindia.org/>

- Address: Uma Manovikas Nagar, Vakalapudi, Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India -533005

- Email address: uets1988@gmail.com
umamanovikasakendram@gmail.com

- Contact number: +91 - 9491220349 , +91 - 0884-2306439 , +91 - 2307097

94. Umeed, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2001

This is an organization/ clinic/training and child development centre for children with developmental disabilities between 2 to 16 years of age. It provides support for parents and teachers.

- Website: <https://ummeed.org>
- Address: Ummeed Child Development Center
Ground Floor, Mantri Pride 1-B, 1/62, N.M. Joshi Marg, Subhash Nagar, Lower Parel, Mumbai 400 011.
6B - 6C Trust House, 6th Floor, Dr. E Borges Road, Near Global Hospital, Parel, Mumbai 400 012

Email address: info@ummeed.org
training@ummeed.org
scheduling.team@ummeed.org

Contact number: +91 22 65528310; 65564054; 23002006 ; 022 6248 8100

95. Urmi Foundation, Mumbai, Maharashtra

Year of establishment: 2011

Website: <https://www.urmifoundation.com/>

Email address: urmi.ngo@gmail.com

Contact number: +91 9152004790

96. USR (Late Sri. Umed Singh Rawat) Indu Samiti, Basai, Peerumadara, Ramnagar, District Nainital

Year of establishment: 1998

Website: <http://usrindusamiti.org/>

Address: U.S.R. Indu Samiti, Village Basai, P.O. Peerumadara, Ramnagar, District Nainital, Uttarakhand, Pin-244715

Email address: usrindusociety@gmail.com

Contact number: 9639582605; +91 – 9412091104

97. Utkarsh Seva Sansthan, Patna, Bihar

Year of establishment: 2017

The organization runs a school for children with autism, down's syndrome, cerebral palsy and

multiple disabilities. It also works with children outside school and provides support to parents.

Website: <http://utkarshsevasansthan.org/>

Address: 2H/77, Bahadurpur Housing Colony, Patna - 800026

E m a i l a d d r e s s :
utkarshsevasansthan@gmail.com
info@utkarshsevasansthan.org

Contact number: 91-8294370626

98. Vatsalyam, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Year of establishment: 1983

It is a day school for 1.5 - 7 year old children with autism spectrum disorder; provides for assessment, counseling & therapy.

Website: <http://www.vatsalyam.in>

Address: Vatsalayam- Centre for Autism No.6/12, II nd Cross Street, L.H.Nagar, 1 st Layout, Adambakkam, Chennai – 600088

Email address: info@vatsalyam.in

Contact number: 9884034323; +9144 24832741 ; +91 9884034323 ; +91 9600198496

99. VISHWAS - Vision for Health Welfare and Special Needs, Gurgaon, Haryana

Year of establishment: 2006

It is a school for children with special needs.

100. We Can India, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Year of establishment: -

The organization has an intervention centre for children of the ages 2 years and above. It specializes in autism spectrum disorder.

Website: www.wecanindia.org

Address: #5, Blue Beach Road, Neelankarai, Chennai 600 115

Email address: wechallengeautism@gmail.com

Contact number: 044-42862221 ; +91-89460-28682